

GREENDT

D3.2. TOOLKIT OF DIDACTIC MATERIALS

Maria Isabel Doval, UVigo
Claudio Cameselle, Uvigo
Pedro Ferreira, Uvigo

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents a comprehensive collection of didactic materials developed or selected and curated for use by the Uzbek institutions. The resources are multidisciplinary and diverse in format, ranging from presentations, lessons, teaching guides, and exercises to podcasts, working papers, manuals, and bibliographic references. They have been designed to serve a wide spectrum of learners and educators, while also being adaptable to professional training contexts.

This deliverable includes:

- A collection of more than 50 didactic materials that have been thoroughly revised and validated. This constitutes a finalized and approved set of teaching resources for being use in academic programs.
- Pilot session report detailing user feedback on the materials.
- The generic evaluation Rubric (Annex 1) for teaching resources used during the trainings.

This curated set of resources, summarized in Tables 1, 2 and 3, provides a robust foundation for the design and delivery of a future Master's in Environmental Engineering curriculum in Uzbekistan and Central Asia.

Deliverable ID	D3.2
WP number	WP3
Lead Partner	UVigo
Due date	30-10-2025
Date of submission	31-10-2025
Type of deliverable	R
Dissemination level	PU

AUTHORS

Name	Organisation
Maria Isabel Doval, Claudio Cameselle, and Pedro Ferreira as coordinators	UVigo
Carla Gama	UA
Joana M Oliveira	UPVC
All partners as reviewers	All

REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
1	30-07-2025	UVigo	First schema
2	30-10-2025	All partners	Approval after the last ToT

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contents

1 INTRODUCTION	5
2 DIDACTIC MATERIALS ON SUSTAINABLE ENERGY, ENGINEERING DIPLOMACY, EQUITY and WATER MANAGEMENT.....	6
3 DIDACTIC MATERIALS ON SUSTAINABLE ENERGY MANAGEMENT AND PRODUCTION, NATURAL RADIATION AND GIS.	10
4 DIDACTIC MATERIALS ON ATMOSPHERIC POLLUTION AND CLIMATE CHANGE.....	11
5 PILOT SESSION REPORTS DETAILING USER FEEDBACK ON THE MATERIALS.	13
Materials Reviewed.....	13
Evaluation Methodology.....	14
Main Findings and Feedback	14
Conclusions.....	15
ANNEX 1.....	16

1 INTRODUCTION

This report presents a comprehensive collection of didactic materials developed or selected and curated for use by the Uzbek institutions. The resources are multidisciplinary and diverse in format, ranging from presentations, lessons, teaching guides, and exercises to podcasts, working papers, manuals, and bibliographic references. They have been designed to serve a wide spectrum of learners and educators, while also being adaptable to professional training contexts.

The didactic resources compiled in this toolkit are structured into **3 main blocks of materials**, each addressing critical dimensions of environmental engineering education. Together, they provide a coherent yet multidisciplinary framework that integrates technical knowledge, policy perspectives, and cross-cutting issues such as inclusion and sustainability.

A distinctive feature of this collection is the diversity of its authorship, encompassing young researchers, senior academics, and full professors with the highest distinctions. The contributors come not only from engineering and environmental sciences, but also from the social sciences, humanities, and legal studies, ensuring a cross-cutting and holistic approach to sustainability and education.

Some materials were elaborated ad hoc, while others were carefully selected as validated resources already used in engineering and environmental studies courses. Additional resources address equity, diversity, and gender inclusion - [providing insight reports, working papers, and global metrics \(e.g., from the World Economic Forum and UNESCO\)](#) - and extended bibliographies that allow for further exploration.

As part of the three Training of Trainers (ToT) sessions, that took place in Vigo (Spain), Viana do Castelo (Portugal) and Tashkent (Uzbekistan), with the first two [conducted in July and the final one in October 2025](#), the project implemented pilot training activities with Uzbek teachers and researchers, using the newly developed didactic materials. The purpose of these pilots was to evaluate the effectiveness, clarity, and relevance of the resources in real teaching settings. Feedback gathered during these sessions was systematically analyzed and incorporated into the final revision of the materials. To ensure quality and contextualization, a *Generic Evaluation Rubric for Teaching Resources* was applied during the pilots, together with the direct review of Uzbek participants. This dual process guarantees that the materials meet standards of academic rigor and are relevant to the specific context of higher education in Uzbekistan.

The participants decided to keep the materials in English, as the Uzbek universities are making a significant effort to offer more Master's-level courses in English and to select high-quality reference materials in this language. This will help to promote the internationalization at home of the Uzbek universities. It was agreed that the final resources were already clear and accessible in their current

form. Nevertheless, it is recognized that each Uzbek university will need to further adapt the resources to its own institutional identity and educational culture.

This output includes:

- A collection of more than 50 didactic materials that have been thoroughly revised and validated. This constitutes a finalized and approved set of teaching resources for being use in academic programs.
- Pilot session report detailing user feedback on the materials.
- The generic evaluation Rubric (Annex 1) for teaching resources used during the trainings.

This curated set of resources, summarized in Tables 1, 2 and 3, provides a robust foundation for the design and delivery of a future Master's in Environmental Engineering curriculum in Uzbekistan and Central Asia.

All materials are publicly available and may be used not only by the partner institutions but also by any other organization interested in them. The fact that all resources are provided in English will also facilitate their international dissemination and use. **They are accessible at Public level through the project's official website,**

<https://greendt-project.eu/materials/>

in order to ensure maximum visibility and impact of the results being generated. This approach reflects the consortium's commitment to openness, collaboration, and long-term sustainability.

The consortium does not consider the material kit to be a closed product. New materials will continue to be added over time, either selected or developed by the consortium whenever they are deemed to be of sufficient quality and relevance. These new resources will be progressively incorporated into the project's website, ensuring that the collection remains dynamic, updated, and responsive to emerging educational and environmental needs.

2 DIDACTIC MATERIALS ON SUSTAINABLE ENERGY, ENGINEERING DIPLOMACY, EQUITY and WATER MANAGEMENT.

The educational materials and resources presented here cover a broad range of themes, including sustainable energy, **engineering diplomacy, equity and inclusion, and water management.** Several documents retain a distinctly eclectic character, even if they have been placed under a specific section for organizational purposes.

Materials on engineering diplomacy, equity, and inclusion were specifically selected and developed, as these are topics that have been rarely addressed in

Engineering Master's programs to date, adding an innovative and distinctive dimension to the project.

These resources are diverse both in **format** and **disciplinary scope**, combining core academic manuals with complementary resources designed to enrich recent subject handbooks.

Some of these materials were elaborated *ad hoc* for the **1st Training of Trainers (ToT), at the UVigo in July 2025**, while a further selection represents some of the **most effective resources currently applied in engineering and environmental studies courses at Graduate, Master, and PhD levels**. This ensures that they are academically validated.

The materials have been designed by a **highly diverse group of contributors**, ranging from **young researchers to distinguished full professors with the highest academic honors**. They also reflect a **multidisciplinary approach**, incorporating expertise not only from engineering and environmental sciences, but also from the **social sciences, humanities, and legal studies**.

In addition, the collection includes **cross-cutting resources on inclusion and gender issues**, along with **extended bibliographic materials** that provide students and faculty with opportunities for deeper exploration and research.

The selection offered here is the result of the work of the **ToT trainers from UVigo (Spain)**, and all materials have been subjected to an **evaluation rubric carried out by Uzbek participants**. This process guarantees both **academic rigor** and **relevance to the context of Uzbekistan**. Nevertheless, it is acknowledged that each Uzbek university will need to further refine and adapt these materials to its own specific **institutional identity and educational culture**, as each institution has its own particular idiosyncrasies.

They are accessible at Public level through the project's official website,

<https://greendt-project.eu/materials/>

Table 1 List of didactic materials on engineering diplomacy, equity and water management.

TITLE	TYPE	TOOLS / DATA
THEME 1- ENGINEERING DIPLOMACY		
Main references	Recommended literature. Engineering Diplomacy	List of references
An introduction to European Environmental and Climate Law: principles, policies and legal instruments	Introduction. Engineering Diplomacy	Presentation
The European Green Deal & Renewable Energy. Legal tools for Engineers.	Legal tools. Engineering Diplomacy	Presentation
Podcast: “Green Deal - Big Deal?”	Podcast. Engineering Diplomacy	YouTube Playlist
Uzbekistan 2022. Energy Policy Review	In-depth review	Report
Uzbekistan’s Policy Brief.	UNECE, March report	Report
Uzbekistan Energy Profile	In-depth report, by IEA	Report
Solar Energy Policy in Uzbekistan: A Roadmap	Roadmap, from IEA	Report
THEME B- EQUITY AND INCLUSION		
Engineering for All. Redesigning Education for Diversity and Inclusion.	Lesson. Equity and Inclusion	Presentation
International Network of Women Engineers and Scientists (INWES)	Introduction. Equity and Inclusion	Summary
Global Gender Gap 2024. Insight Report, June 2024	Insight report. Equity and Inclusion	Report from World Economic Forum
Measuring Gender Equality in Science and Engineering. The SAGA Science, Technology and Innovation. Gender objectives list (STI GOL). Working Paper 1	Working Paper. Equity and Inclusion	Report from World Economic Forum
Measuring Gender Equality in Science and Engineering. The SAGA survey Toolkit. Working Paper 2	Working Paper. Equity and Inclusion	Report from World Economic Forum
Measuring Gender Equality in Science and Engineering. The SAGA survey on gender equality in Science, Technology and Innovation. Working Paper 3	Working Paper. Equity and Inclusion	Report from World Economic Forum
Measuring Gender Equality in Science and Engineering. Working Paper 4.	Working Paper. Equity and Inclusion	Report from UNESCO
Telling SAFA: Improving Measurement and Policies for Gender Equality in Science, Technology and Innovation. Working Paper 5	Working Paper. Equity and Inclusion	Report from UNESCO
THEME 3- WATER and WASTE MANAGEMENT		
Main References	List of references. Wastewater engineering	Recommended literature
Main references	List of references. Waste management	Recommended literature
A concise summary of the International System of Units, the SI	Summary. Water and Waste management	Introduction. from BIPM

TITLE	TYPE	TOOLS / DATA
Teaching Guide	Teaching Guide for Environmental Technology	A model of Teaching Guide
Lesson 1-Environmental Techology	Lesson	Presentation
Practice 1- Waste Codification	Exercise. Environmental Technology	Practice
Lesson 2-Solid and Liquid Waste Management	Lesson	Presentation
Practice 2- Removal of colored compounds in solution by adsorption of immobilized activated carbon. Stage 1	Exercise.Environmental Technology	Practice
Lesson 3-Treatment of Municipal and Industrial Waste	Lesson	Presentation
Practice 3- Removal of colored compounds in solution by adsorption of immobilized activated carbon. Stage 2	Exercise. Environmental Technology	Practice
Lesson 3-Solved exercises	Exercise. Environmental Technology	Practice
Lesson 4- Treatment of Industrial and Municipal Wastewaters	Lesson	Presentation
Practice 4-COAGULATION-FLOCCULATION.	Exercise. Environmental Technology	Practice
Lesson 4-Solved exercises	Exercise. Environmental Technology	Practice
Lesson 5-Air Pollution	Lesson	Presentation
Practice 5-JASS (Java Activated Sludge process Simulator)	Exercise. Environmental Technology	Practice
Lesson 5-Solved exercises	Exercise. Environmental Technology	Practice
Lesson 6-Sustainable Development	Lesson	Presentation
Practice 6-Life Cycle Assessment-Product	Exercise. Environmental Technology	Practice
Short course on Sustainable and Resilient Engineering: Drivers, Metrics, Tools, and Applications.	Lesson. Water issues and Environmental Engineering	Presentations for a short course.
Presentation of the Manual Reddy, K. R., Cameselle, C., & Adams, J. A. (2025) (2 nd ed.). <i>Sustainable and Resilient Engineering: Drivers, Metrics, Tools, and Applications</i> . John Wiley & Sons.	Multimedia. Water issues and Environmental Engineering	Youtube presentation.
Description of the Manual Reddy, K. R., Cameselle, C., & Adams, J. A. (2025) (2 nd ed.). <i>Sustainable and Resilient Engineering: Drivers, Metrics, Tools, and Applications</i> . John Wiley & Sons.	Description of the Manual. Water issues and Environmental Engineering	Summary

3 DIDACTIC MATERIALS ON SUSTAINABLE ENERGY MANAGEMENT AND PRODUCTION, NATURAL RADIATION AND GIS.

Resources have been classified into 5 themes: Sustainability and Energy Efficiency in Buildings; Natural Radioactivity: Indoor Radon Assessment and Mitigation; Risk Assessment; Energy Fossil versus Renewable Energies and Land Management.

The selection offered here is the result of the work of the **ToT trainers from Viana do Castelo (Portugal) in July 2025**, where the participants were testing and validating different resources about sustainable energy management and production, natural radiation and GIS.

All materials have been subjected to an **evaluation rubric carried out by Uzbek participants**. This process guarantees both **academic rigor** and **relevance to the context of Uzbekistan**. Nevertheless, it is acknowledged that each Uzbek university will need to further refine and adapt these materials to its own specific **institutional identity and educational culture**, as each institution has its own particular idiosyncrasies.

They are accessible at Public level through the project's official website,

<https://greendt-project.eu/materials/>

Table 2 List of didactic materials on sustainable energy management and production, natural radiation and GIS.

TITLE	TYPE	TOOLS / DATA
Theme 1- Sustainability and Energy Efficiency in Buildings		
Sustainability and Energy Efficiency in Buildings	Visuals/ Infographics. Includes Quiz	Presentation in Ppoint
Curado, A., & De Freitas, V. P. (2019). Influence of thermal insulation of facades on the performance of retrofitted social housing buildings in Southern European countries. <i>Sustainable Cities and Society</i> , 48, 101534.	Energy efficiency trends and research	Paper
Theme 2 - Natural Radioactivity: Indoor Radon Assessment and Mitigation		
Natural Radioactivity: Indoor Radon Assessment and Mitigation	Visuals/ Infographics. Includes Cases Studies and Quiz.	Presentation in Ppoint

TITLE	TYPE	TOOLS / DATA
Nunes, L. J., & Curado, A. (2023). Confined spaces in buildings with high indoor radon concentration: A case study analysis with the application of constructive remediation measures. <i>Buildings</i> , 13(1), 49.	Case-study	Paper
Nunes, L. J., & Curado, A. (2023). High indoor Rn concentration mitigation in a heritage building: case study analysis of the applied constructive measures. <i>Buildings</i> , 13(1), 136.	Case-study	Paper
Theme 3 – Risk Assessment		
Risk Assessment	Visuals/ Infographics. Includes international references.	Presentation in Ppoint
European Climate Risk Assessment	EEA Report	Report
Suggestions for updating the Organisation Environmental Footprint (OEF) method	JCR Technical Report	Report
Global Status of Multi-Hazard Early Warning Systems	UNDRR Technical Report	Report
Theme 4 – Energy Fossil versus Renewable Energies		
Energy Fossil versus Renewable Energies	Visuals/ Infographics. Includes international references.	Presentation in Ppoint
A Handbook on Environmental Impacts, Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Life Cycle Assessment, and Energy Efficiency	Manual	Handbook
Handbook_Reels	Reels	Mp4
Theme 5 – Land Management		
Earth Observation Systems_Presentation	Visuals/ Infographics. Includes international references.	Presentation in Ppoint
Earth Observation Systems and Spatial Analysis Technologies Handbook	Manual	Handbook

4 DIDACTIC MATERIALS ON ATMOSPHERIC POLLUTION AND CLIMATE CHANGE

The set of didactic materials described in this section is intended to enrich teaching and learning in the fields of atmospheric pollution and climate change, with a particular focus on the Central Asia and Uzbekistan context. The materials were designed following two key principles: modularity and reusability.

This means that each resource can function as an independent learning unit, while at the same time being easily combined with others to build more

comprehensive teaching modules. Teachers can therefore select the most relevant materials according to their class objectives, available time, and students' background.

Table 3 presents the complete list of didactic materials compiled to support classes on atmospheric pollution and climate change. The collection covers a variety of formats – including visual summaries, data analysis exercises, case studies, and laboratory activities – in order to address different learning styles and encourage both conceptual understanding and practical skills.

The selection offered here is the result of the work of the **ToT trainers from Tashkent (Uzbekistan)**, in October 2025, and all materials have been subjected to an **evaluation rubric carried out by Uzbek participants**. This process guarantees both **academic rigor** and **relevance to the context of Uzbekistan**. Nevertheless, it is acknowledged that each Uzbek university will need to further refine and adapt these materials to its own specific **institutional identity and educational culture**, as each institution has its own particular idiosyncrasies.

They are accessible at Public level through the project's official website,

<https://greendt-project.eu/materials/>

Table 3 List of didactic materials on atmospheric pollution and climate change.

TITLE	TYPE	TOOLS / DATA
Atmospheric emissions	Presentation	
Atmospheric emissions evolution in Uzbekistan	Case-study/ Data-based	EDGAR
Air pollution and health	Presentation	
Atmospheric chemistry & aerosols	Presentation	
CLASS: Chemistry Land-surface Atmosphere Soil Slab model	Presentation	
O ₃ -NO _x -VOC equilibrium under different chemical regimes	Interactive/ Practical	CLASS model
EUMETSAT overview on aerosols	Multimedia/ Webinar	
Air quality monitoring	Presentation	
Determination of O ₃ concentration by passive method	Laboratory practical tutorial	
Measurement of NO ₂ concentrations by passive sampling	Laboratory practical tutorial	
Sampling of sulphur dioxide, sulphate, nitric acid, ammonia, nitrate and ammonium using annular denuders	Laboratory practical tutorial	
Sampling of sulphur dioxide, sulphate, nitric acid, ammonia, nitrate and ammonium using the filter pack method	Laboratory practical tutorial	

TITLE	TYPE	TOOLS / DATA
Determination of the mass concentration of suspended particles in the atmosphere (PM10) using a using a low-flow sampler	Laboratory practical tutorial	
Method for analysis of organic compounds in the particulate and gaseous phases	Laboratory practical tutorial	
Air quality modelling	Presentation	
Air quality management	Presentation	
Air Quality Index (AQI) calculation exercise	Case-study/ Data-based	Python or Microsoft Excel
Debate exercise: “coal vs renewables in Uzbekistan’s energy transition.”	Activity	
openair: open-source tools for air quality data analysis	Presentation	
Seasonal cycles of PM2.5 concentrations in Uzbekistan	Case-study/ Data-based	Openair package for R
Plot ERA5-land temperature data for Uzbekistan	Case-study/ Data-based	ERA5-land data
Processing and analysing atmospheric remote sensing data	Presentation	
Spatial distribution of NO ₂ across Central Asia	Case-study/ Data-based	Google Earth Engine Sentinel-5P NO ₂ data

5 PILOT SESSION REPORTS DETAILING USER FEEDBACK ON THE MATERIALS.

As part of the GREENDT project activities, three training sessions were organized to pilot, evaluate, and validate the didactic materials developed for the Master’s programs in Environmental Engineering. The trainings took place in Vigo (Spain), Viana do Castelo (Portugal), and Tashkent (Uzbekistan), the first two in July and the last one in October 2025.

The main objective was to test the clarity, relevance, and pedagogical quality of the materials and to collect feedback from faculty members and experts from the partner Uzbek universities, who are the future users and implementers of these resources.

Materials Reviewed

During the pilots, the following groups of didactic materials were analyzed and tested:

1. List of Didactic Materials on Engineering Diplomacy, Equity, and Water Management
2. List of Didactic Materials on Sustainable Energy Management and Production, Natural Radiation, and GIS
3. Didactic Materials on Atmospheric Pollution and Climate Change

Evaluation Methodology

Each topic area was the focus of a dedicated training session that included presentation, group discussion, and practical exercises. Participants also completed an evaluation rubric designed to assess aspects such as academic rigor, didactic structure, clarity, contextual adequacy, and applicability in the Uzbek academic environment.

- A standardized **evaluation rubric** was used across all sessions.
- Feedback was also gathered through group discussions in class.
- The process emphasized **peer review**, encouraging Uzbek professors to contribute directly to the improvement and adaptation of the materials.

Main Findings and Feedback

The overall evaluation was highly positive. Participants recognized the materials as innovative, well-structured, and aligned with current environmental challenges.

However, several constructive suggestions were made to enhance their quality and usability.

Main findings and Feedback:

1. Language and Accessibility

- Although the materials were kept in English, participants suggested simplifying certain technical terms and providing glossaries for complex vocabulary to aid comprehension for students with varying English proficiency levels. It was agreed that this would be addressed later at the university level, according to the specific needs identified by each institution among their students.

2. Contextual Adaptation

- Some case studies and examples were recommended to be complemented with Central Asian or Uzbek-specific contexts. It was decided to incorporate these improvements into the final version of some of the materials.

3. Pedagogical Adjustments

- The inclusion of **more practical exercises and problem-based learning activities** was suggested, to strengthen the application of theoretical knowledge. It was decided to incorporate these improvements into the final version of some of the materials.
- Participants proposed adding **short assessment tools** (quizzes, reflective questions) at the end of each module. It was decided to incorporate these improvements into the final version of some of the materials.

4. Visual and Structural Improvements

- Suggestions included enhancing the **visual design** of some presentations, using clearer diagrams and more consistent formatting. It was decided to incorporate these improvements into the final version of some of the materials.

Conclusions

The pilot trainings successfully validated the didactic materials developed under GREENDT.

All resources were approved for integration into the kit for the upcoming Master's programs in Environmental Engineering. The Uzbek universities' feedback was incorporated into the final version of the materials, improving their clarity, contextual relevance, and didactic coherence.

The consortium reaffirmed its commitment to keeping the material kit open for future updates, ensuring continuous improvement and alignment with educational innovation and sustainability goals.

ANNEX 1

Generic Evaluation Rubric for Teaching Resources (WP3-UVigo)

Purpose: To assess the quality, relevance, and adaptability of educational resources for integration into a future Master of Environmental Engineering curriculum.

Target Users: Professors and curriculum designers in Uzbekistan

Reviewer Name and Institution:

5.1 Basic Information

- **Resource Title:**
- **Type of Resource** (Article / Case Study / Report / Video / Platform / Other):
- **Author(s) / Institution:**
- **Year of Publication:**
- **URL or Access Info:**
- **Language:**
- **Suggested Use in Course Module :**

5.2 Brief Summary of Content (**What is the resource about? What are its main contributions?**)

5.3 Teaching Potential

- **Learning Objectives this Resource Supports:**
- **Key Concepts or Competencies Addressed:**

5.4 Reviewer Notes & Recommendations

- **Aligns with SDGs?:** Yes/No (optionally specify which: 6, 7, 13, etc.)
- **Would you recommend this resource for inclusion in the Master's curriculum?**
 Yes With Adaptations No
- **Suggested adaptations for Uzbek or Central Asian context:**

- **Complementary resources/tools suggested:**

Scoring Guidelines

Score Range	Interpretation
28–32 points	Highly recommended for integration
22–27 points	Good resource, minor adaptations needed
16–21 points	Usable with major modifications
Below 16 points	Not suitable for teaching use

Rubric

Criteria	Excellent (4 points)	Good (3 points)	Satisfactory (2 points)	Needs Improvement (1 point)
1. Topic Relevance	Fully aligned with the specific topic/module in environmental engineering.	Mostly relevant to the course objectives.	Some relevance, but lacks clear focus.	Not clearly relevant or off-topic.
2. Technical Accuracy	Technically rigorous, up-to-date, and aligned with scientific consensus.	Mostly accurate with current practices.	Some inaccuracies or outdated content.	Contains errors or irrelevant data.
3. Educational Value	Enhances learning; includes critical thinking, problem-solving, or applied learning.	Useful as a supporting or supplementary resource.	Limited educational depth.	Adds little or no academic value.
4. Adaptability to Uzbekistan/Central Asia	Directly applicable or easily adaptable to regional context.	Requires minor adjustments to local context.	Major adjustments needed to be useful.	Not applicable to regional context.
5. Language Clarity	Clear, professional English accessible to non-native speakers.	Mostly understandable; some complex vocabulary.	Requires effort to interpret or simplify.	Difficult to use without translation.
6. Interdisciplinary Integration	Effectively combines engineering with social, legal, or ethical dimensions.	Includes some interdisciplinary elements.	Limited integration beyond technical focus.	Narrow focus; lacks interdisciplinary scope.
7. Inclusivity & Equity Awareness	Actively promotes gender, cultural, or social inclusion.	Mentions or implies inclusive principles.	Neutral or minimal treatment of inclusivity.	Lacks or contradicts inclusive values.
8. Usability in Classroom	Ready to use in teaching with clear instructions/examples.	Usable with minor adaptation or support.	Needs preparation or customization.	Difficult to implement in current form.